

The Mediation Effect of Fear of Contracting an Epidemic Disease Between Real Estate Customers' Decision-Making Styles and Their Expectations from Digital Technologies

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Abstract

Written within the current global Covid-19 pandemic, which has given rise to unparalleled global ramifications, necessitating significant adjustments in personal and professional spheres, and exposing the inadequacy of conventional corporate processes and standards. The enduring impacts of individuals' future trajectories have been influenced by the experiences and tactics they have acquired while endeavoring to surmount a crisis.

The study used a multidimensional approach in its analysis of the topic. The research started by seeking to determine the anticipated preferences and

requirements of clients inside the digital realm of the real estate sector. Following this, the elements that influence these expectations were found. The primary purpose of this research was to examine decision-making styles and investigate the consumer attitudes that underlie these styles. The aim was to get a deeper understanding of how consumers use digital technologies to facilitate their decision-making process. A study was conducted to investigate the impact of psychological variables, namely the fear of Covid, on decision-making processes and expectancies within the context of a crisis scenario. Simultaneously, a study was done to evaluate the impact of fear on customer attitudes and decision-making processes.

Consequently, the study yielded data that indicate a mediation role of worry over Covid-19 in the relationship between decision-making styles and the expectations of real estate clients towards digital technology.

Keywords: Mediation Effect, Fear of Contracting, Epidemic Disease, Real Estate Customers' Decision-Making Styles, Expectations from Digital Technologies

Introduction

The adverse effects seen during the Covid-19 pandemic have significantly transformed global economic and social landscapes. The experiences encountered over the COVID-19 pandemic have given rise to newfound awareness and prompted a reassessment of requirements for the era after the pandemic. Concurrently, individuals have become more reliant on digital technology. The use of digital technology by consumers facilitated a heightened awareness of the shortcomings present in current designs, thereby leading to a shift in their expectations pertaining to digital surroundings. The real estate industry has faced significant challenges in marketing throughout the pandemic, rendering typical marketing approaches ineffective. To address these adverse aspects, it has become imperative to provide innovative modifications to the design frameworks of the technologies used in the realm of digital marketing. The demands of real estate clients regarding the utilization of technology settings in real estate marketing are progressively escalating. To effectively fulfill the growing expectations in the field of digital media design, designers must accurately identify and assess the demands and requirements, as well as thoroughly examine the elements that influence these expectations. The main objective of this study was to ascertain the anticipated outcomes of real estate consumers in relation to digital technology. One of the responsibilities assigned to marketers is to influence and mold the decision-making frameworks of clients, so aiding them in their purchase choices. Given the high cost, variability, extensive use of materials, and potential for serving as an investment vehicle, buyers are faced with the need to carefully assess a multitude of factors when deciding to acquire real estate goods. The effective management of gathered data presents challenges in the decision-making process. The essential concern in digital media designs is on effectively delivering pertinent product information to clients in a lucid manner. The primary objective of information collection is to enhance the process of decision making. Various decision-making styles are used by customers throughout the decision-making process. This research examines the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on consumer psychology, specifically focusing on the mediating role of COVID-19 dread in the relationship between decision-making styles and real estate clients' expectations in digital contexts.

Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies

When analyzing the evolution of real estate marketing, it becomes evident that the market environment first emerged via the facilitation of real estate brokers who acted as intermediaries, connecting buyers and sellers. The market environment has undergone a transformation due to the increased demand of real estate clients for a larger range of alternatives and the sellers' inclination to offer their properties in a broader market context. The inclination to disseminate and exchange information with a wide audience has led individuals and businesses to engage with media platforms. During the first phase, the primary medium used was mostly newspapers (Washington Territory Real Estate, 2023). However, the media provided only a limited amount of information on the properties that were sold, with little emphasis on specific specifics. The use of local newspapers for advertising purposes resulted in a constrained outreach to a certain demographic. The use of the television medium was limited owing to its exorbitant expenses and constrained advertising time. The rapid emergence of the internet in the 1990s facilitated the swift dissemination of real estate advertisements for sale online (Baen & Guttery, 1997) (Hamilton, 2007). The growth of the real estate market, facilitated by online marketing, has not kept pace with the rapid sales expansion seen in other e-commerce sectors. This discrepancy may be attributed to the inherent limitations of conducting property transactions directly via online platforms.

Real estate properties are often tangible commodities that are visually seen by potential buyers and desired for purchase. In recent times, there has been a development in the creation of virtual environments to cater to the demands of clients via online platforms. In this regard, attempts have been made to provide virtual tours of residential properties by simulating genuine residences (Chen & Yao, 2022). Several research have yielded findings pertaining to the emotional responses of consumers when they interact with virtual surroundings that closely resemble actual ones. The focus of inquiry in this research is to the potential of virtual journeys to stimulate clients' purchasing intentions. Azmi, Ibrahim, and Ghafar (2021) have acquired results indicating that the stimulation of the propensity to purchase is positively influenced.

In contemporary times, the act of physically seeing and observing a real estate property is deemed insufficient for clients in the process of making a purchase. In order to make an informed purchasing choice, it is essential to consider supplementary and comprehensive data pertaining to many factors. For instance, it would be beneficial to examine the socioeconomic

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standing of the neighboring residents, the caliber of education offered in nearby educational institutions, and the speed of internet connectivity as part of the local infrastructure (Bond, Seiler, Seiler, & Blake, 2000).

In contemporary online market situations, where real estate marketing is prevalent, it has been observed that the information provided to clients is inadequate in meeting their growing demands. Customers have a need for enhanced access to information on financial assistance, investment profitability, energy efficiency, and the provision of advisory services as and when required. The recognition of the potential of machines to enhance human lives has emerged with advancements in artificial intelligence technologies. In contemporary society, buyers possess a prevailing anticipation for the seamless acquisition of knowledge and immediate communication facilitated by various technological instruments. Furthermore, it has been noted by Lopez, Del Monte, and Montero (2008) that digital environments integrated with artificial intelligence play a crucial role in facilitating the purchase decision-making process.

Fear of Conceiving an Epidemic in Orientation to Digital Technologies in Real Estate Marketing

According to Grum and Grum (2015), emotional and motivational components exhibit a high degree of sensitivity to environmental circumstances. The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in a significant impact on the general population, leading to heightened levels of adverse emotional states. Scholars have characterized this epidemic as a substantial social catastrophe that induces psychological distress (Wang et al., 2021). The primary affective consequence experienced by individuals in response to COVID-19 is dread.

The emotional influence of COVID-19 on individuals include fear, which may be analyzed and understood via four distinct levels. The identified fears in relation to the illness may be categorized as follows: firstly, the fear of disease transmission into one's own body; secondly, the fear of those of high social standing contracting the disease; thirdly, the fear stemming from inadequate knowledge about the disease; and finally, the fear of making incorrect decisions or taking inappropriate actions (Schimmenti, Billieux, & Starcevic, 2020).

When considering the acquisition of real estate post-pandemic, it is crucial for real estate marketers to comprehend the potential shifts in individuals' attitudes and behaviors resulting from their experiences during the pandemic, as well as the anticipation of future epidemics.

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The COVID-19 pandemic has introduced significant uncertainty into brokerage activity within the real estate marketing sector. The implementation of social distancing measures at the individual level has prompted buyers, sellers, and intermediaries to reassess their customary daily routines and devise alternative strategies for conducting transactions. Real estate brokers have been required to provide prospective purchasers with more assurances on their health. According to Nicola et al. (2020), several brokers have used communication platforms such as FaceTime, Zoom, and WhatsApp to conduct their meetings, while also using Skype for coordinating home tours. This approach aims to mitigate the potential transmission of illness.

Similar to other regions globally, during this particular period in Ireland and England, prospective buyers of real estate were unable to engage in joint property tours with real estate agents, and property appraisers were unable to conduct actual visits to the properties in question. According to Greene and Devine (2020), the use of virtual home tours using computers and mobile phones facilitated by the Internet saw a decline in client interest levels by 60% at the conclusion of March 2020, in comparison to the same time in 2019.

During this particular time frame, virtual reality was used as a digital marketing instrument within the context of China. Several real estate brokers in China have indicated that virtual tour experiences are effective for promotional purposes. However, clients often find the information obtained from virtual tours to be inadequate when making purchase decisions, as they prefer to physically see the properties for sale. Simultaneously, it has been asserted by brokers that the virtual tour application yields a limited number of sales. Furthermore, it has been observed that consumers who use this way to make purchases possess a high-income level, and often employ this approach when acquiring a second or third home for investment objectives (Brown, 2020).

Decision-Making Styles Influencing Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies

The use of digital technology by real estate clients is driven by the anticipation that such tools would facilitate their decision-making process. The concept of "decision making" is often seen as the manifestation of choice behavior (Connor & Becker, 2003). In order to ensure the

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proper execution of the real estate marketing process by intermediary businesses and manufacturers, it is important to accurately understand the elements that influence consumers' decision-making behavior.

Behavioral problems often arise as a result of the expectations that real estate customers have about their requirements being fulfilled. Occasionally, consumers are able to explicitly articulate their wants, however in other instances, certain requirements may elude customers' awareness, but may be uncovered via the diligent efforts of marketers. The aforementioned criteria are referred to as fuzzy factors in the study conducted by Lopez, Santos, and Montero (2010) on fuzzy specification in real estate market decision-making. The components that are explicitly articulated are associated with the cognitive aspect of attitude, whilst the ones that are less clearly defined are often those that may be assessed within the emotional aspect of attitude. When faced with a purchase decision, buyers often have the option to use either a logical decision-making style, which relies on analysis, or an intuitive decision-making style, which is based on emotions. This choice is made after gathering relevant information about the goods. The individual often employs a hybrid decision-making approach, including elements of both intellectual and emotional considerations. Prior to reaching a choice, consumers often rely on the perspectives of others, draw from their previous encounters to make prompt judgments, or choose to refrain from making a decision (Scott & Bruce, 1995). The emotional decision-making style in real estate marketing garners attention from both production businesses and marketers. Research done in Japan using the Kansei engineering technique yielded the finding that a linear correlation exists between the emotional states of clients in the real estate sector and their decision-making processes when it comes to acquiring properties (Llinares & Page, 2011). Real estate clientele often uses five distinct decision structures in the process of making selections. The many decision-making styles include rational choice making, intuitive decision making, rapid decision making, reliant decision making, and decision avoidance.

Rational decision making

Greater emphasis and dedication are allocated towards the logical decision-making process. In times of heightened ambiguity and mounting skepticism over potential resolutions, individuals often engage in self-critique by striving for coherence with prior choices and

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decisions. Following a thorough examination of the relevant particulars, individuals endeavor to identify and implement optimal options in order to address the issue at hand.

At the conclusion of the cognitive process, it is anticipated that consumers would engage in decision-making that is characterized by rationality. In the field of economics, individuals that exhibit rational decision-making are often referred to as Homo Economicus. The preferences that please sensible beings are in alignment with their wants. According to Urbina and Villaverde (2019), these persons are characterized as individuals who have made a choice that will yield the most advantage for themselves and, eventually, for society. Rationality may be regarded as the foundational element in the realm of consumer choice process study. Nevertheless, some study findings have shown that consumers deviate from rationality in their decision-making processes in the latter stages. The observed disparity may be attributed to variations in individuals' evaluative capacities, as influenced by factors such as crises, economic instability, limited alternatives, differentiation of cognitive talents, restricted information, and diverse emotional inclinations (Kamber, 2018). Due to this rationale, there exists a tendency to embrace the notion of limited rationality, first introduced by Herbert A. Simon, as opposed to absolute rationality.

A rational consumer may be described as an individual who utilizes available knowledge and computational tools to make logical and sensible judgments. The use of restricted information during decision-making processes, particularly in contexts characterized by uncertainty, might provide challenges in accurately understanding the external environment. The presence of non-rational processes, such as motivation, emotions, and sensory inputs, throughout the process of reasoning leads individuals to try to understand a situation by directing their attention. Consequently, the idea of limited rationality seems to be a more realistic and logical framework, as opposed to the notion of pure rationality. According to Simon (1986), one may argue that it is an approach. The human body has cognitive and emotional capacities that enable it to effectively address challenges arising from its environment. Habits serve to optimize and streamline human behaviors. Habits are acquired as a result of the process of learning. The process of acquiring knowledge and insights from the consequences of previous erroneous choices facilitates the ability to make more accurate and effortless options in subsequent instances. The significance of habit stability is seen crucial not

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just at the individual level but also within the context of society. The use of practical thinking offers a convenient means through which several challenges may be effectively surmounted. The aforementioned scenario underscores the need of using intuitive decision-making strategies when confronted with novel challenges (Twomey, 1998).

Intuitive decision making

Intuitive decision making encompasses the utilization of familiarity, recognition, similarity, awareness, simple relationships, and simple causal connections. This approach facilitates the resolution of recurring problems and the exploration of uncomplicated solutions for complex problems, particularly in situations characterized by limited information availability. During situations that demand prompt decision-making with limited time, individuals prefer to rely more on intuitive decision-making due to its ability to operate swiftly, in contrast to the slower pace of logical decision-making.

The efficacy of intuition is compromised under states of emotional disturbance and unhappiness. When an individual experiences positive affect, their creative thinking may be enhanced via the use of intuitive decision-making processes. However, it is important to note that engaging in impulsive activities might lead to the occurrence of logical errors. In his seminal work, Kahneman (2003) coined the terms "system 1" and "system 2" to refer to the intuitive and logical decision-making processes, respectively. The second system assumes the responsibility of verifying the suggestions generated by the first system. Individuals typically exhibit a preference for intuitive decision-making, commonly referred to as the first system. However, in scenarios characterized by novelty or limited information, the rational decision-making process, or the second system, becomes necessary. This process compels individuals to engage in decision-making that aligns with their innate inclinations. The individual noted that as a result of inertia, system 2 often exhibits a propensity to endorse the choices formulated by system 1.

Dependent decision making

The dependent decision-making style refers to a decision-making approach characterized by an individual's reliance on others for assistance in making choices, since they are unable to

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independently arrive at decisions. This decision-making approach involves actively seeking the views and guidance of others. In instances of this kind, individuals may have feelings of inadequacy when faced with decision-making, prompting a reliance on external validation for their choices. According to Bodin, Chermack, and Coons (2016), Customers often adopt a dependent decision-making style when faced with high-priced products or products that include complicated features. In contemporary times, the extensive array of choices and functionalities inherent in consumer items poses a challenge in terms of doing thorough research and arriving at informed selections. The inclusion of customer reviews facilitates the decision-making process for potential buyers by providing insights from those who have previously purchased and used the product. Within the realm of digital marketing, a plethora of websites exist, all vying to provide assistance to clients in this regard. In recent times, there has been a notable increase in the preference for digital marketing platforms as a means of purchasing. This may be attributed to the presence of software embedded inside shopping websites, which facilitates convenient comparison of costs and product attributes for consumers.

Quick decision making

The concept of quick decision-making pertains to the act of making immediate choices. The decision-making style in question is often used under circumstances characterized by a pressing need for prompt decision-making. According to the study conducted by Bovolar and Orosova in 2015, The practice of using price as a primary determinant in the decision-making process for items that possess limited characteristics and are relatively inexpensive is a common occurrence. Nevertheless, the use of this decision-making technique becomes challenging when acquiring high-priced things with several characteristics, such as real estate. The quick decision-making style is characterized by a propensity for making decisions rapidly, which is associated with a higher level of risk. In situations when prompt decision-making is required, it is possible that essential information necessary for making an informed choice may be absent. The accuracy of the assessment may be compromised as a result of insufficient information. Real estate goods are assets that have the potential to safeguard their value over an extended period of time. The purchases made by individuals are seen to possess relatively lower levels of risk compared to other investment vehicles. In fact, these purchases may be regarded as risk-

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mitigating items when acquired in conjunction with other investment instruments. During times characterized by price inflation, clients who engage in early purchasing might get advantages from their transactions in comparison to those who make purchases at a later time. However, the duration for the return of the invested price to the consumer may vary depending on the kind of real estate acquired, as a consequence of purchasing in an inappropriate area. While it is advisable to use caution when making real estate purchases, it is as important to avoid delaying the choice by carefully monitoring economic indicators.

Avoid making decisions

The use of this particular decision-making approach is often seen in situations characterized by a significant degree of ambiguity, intricate product attributes, and an indeterminate assessment of the potential benefits associated with the intended purchase. Individuals who choose for this particular approach to decision-making often exhibit a tendency to defer and postpone the decision-making process, so reserving contemplation and implementation of a solution until a later occasion. According to Burhanoglu (2016), Individuals who use this particular approach to decision-making tend to defer making judgments until they experience mounting pressure, maybe due to the discomfort elicited by the matter under consideration (Rotbring, 2010).

RESEARCH METHOD

Universe and Sample

The scope of this study encompasses the whole population of individuals who engage in real estate transactions. The sample comprises 433 individuals with varying characteristics such as age, gender, income level, education level, number of households, and jobs. These individuals may be accessed via social media platforms and have shown interest in participating in the survey.

Data Collection Method and Tool

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The study used a questionnaire as the chosen approach for data gathering. The survey was administered using the Google Documents survey tool, and it was disseminated to participants using internet communication apps. Participants were given the opportunity to provide their responses to the survey using both their PCs and mobile devices.

Scales Used in the Study

During the formulation of the study questions, three distinct scales were used. The independent variable decision-making styles were determined using the "General Decision-Making Styles Scale" developed by Scott and Bruce in 1995. The "Covid Fear Scale," developed in 2020 by Ahorsu, Lin, Imani, Saffari, Griffiths, and Pakpour, was used to assess the level of dread associated with the Covid-19 pandemic. This scale served as the mediator variable in the study. The dependent variable, namely the expectation of real estate customers for digital technologies, was identified by an extensive literature analysis and investigation of current and emerging digital marketing practices (Ahorsu et al., 2020).

Statistical Analysis Methods

The data analysis was conducted using the SPSS package software and the AMOS program. The scales established for each variable were subjected to reliability analysis and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) using the SPSS software package. The AMOS software was used to conduct confirmatory factor analyses (CFA), route analyses, and structural equation model (SEM) analyses.

Findings and Interpretation

Table 1. Demographic Information

Demographic Information		f_i	%
Age	18-30	270	62.4
	31-45	98	22.6
	46-55	48	11.1

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	56-65	9	2.1
	66 years and older	8	1.8
	Total	433	100.0
Gender	Woman	203	46.9
	Male	230	53.1
	Total	433	100.0
Income Level	1-5000	258	59.6
	6000 - 10 000	121	27.9
	11 000 – 15 000	33	7.6
	16 000 – 20 000	13	3.0
	21 000 and above	8	1.8
	Total	433	100.0
Job	Officer	84	19.4
	Private Sector employee	55	12.7
	Self-employment	23	5.3
	Farmer	7	1.6
	Employee	26	6.0
	Retired	14	3.2
	Student	187	43.2
	Housewife	20	4.6
	Not working	17	3.9
	Total	433	100.0
Education level	Primary education	15	3,5
	secondary education	56	12.9
	Associate Degree	132	30.5
	License	200	46.2
	graduate	30	6.9
	Total	433	100.0
Number of Households	one	28	6.5
	2	56	12.9

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	3	102	23.6
	4	124	28.6
	5 and above	123	28.4
	Total	433	100.0

Upon examination of Table 1, it is seen that 62.4% (n=270) of the participants fall into the age range of "18-30". Additionally, 22.6% (n=98) of the participants are categorized within the age range of "31-45". Furthermore, it is noted that 11.1% of the participants also belong to the "31-45" age range. Among the sample population of 48 individuals, it was observed that 2.1% (n=9) fell into the age range of 56-65, while 1.8% (n=8) were classified as being 66 years old or older. Upon analyzing the participants with respect to the gender variable, it was observed that 53.1% (n=230) of the participants identified as "male," while 46.9% (n=203) identified as "female." When analyzing the participants in the study with respect to the variable of income level, it was found that 59.6% (n=256) fell within the range of "1-5,000TL". Additionally, 27.9% (n=121) reported an income between "6,000-10,000TL". A smaller proportion of participants, specifically 7% (n=33), indicated an income range of "11,000 – 15,000 TL". Furthermore, 3% (n=13) reported an income between "16,000 – 20,000 TL", while 1.8% (n=8) stated an income of "21,000 TL and above". It seems that the individual has a source of financial earnings. When categorizing the participants based on their occupation, it was found that 43.2% (n=187) identified as "students," 19.4% (n=84) as "civil servants," and 12.7% (n=55) as "private" individuals. In the study, it was found that 10.1% (n=44) of the participants identified themselves as "professionals", while 9.2% (n=40) identified as "students". Additionally, 8.3% (n=36) of the respondents identified as "business owners", 6% (n=26) as "employees in the public sector", 5.3% (n=23) as "workers", and 4.6% (n=20) The data reveals that a proportion of 3.9% (n=17) may be classified as "not working," while 3.2% (n=14) fall into the category of "retired." Additionally, a smaller percentage of 1.6% (n=7) can be identified as "farmers." When the participants are categorized based on their level of education, it is seen that 46.2% (n=200) have an "undergraduate" degree, 30.5% (n=132) have an "associate degree", and 12.9% (n=56) have a "graduate degree". The data reveals that 6.9% (n=30) of the participants possess a "secondary education" level, while another 6.9% (n=30) have attained a "graduate" level of

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education. Additionally, 3.5% (n=15) of the participants have completed their schooling at the "primary education" level. When examining the participants in relation to the variable of household numbers, it was found that 28.6% (n=124) belonged to the category labeled "4", while 28.4% (n=123) fell into the category labeled "5 and above". Additionally, 23.6% (n=102) of participants were categorized as "3", 12.9% (n=56) as "2", and 6.5% (n=28) as "1".

Table 2. Information about Covid

Information about Covid-19		f_i	%
I had Covid-19.	Yes	149	34.4
	No	284	65.6
I got the Covid-19 vaccine.	Yes	404	93.3
	No	29	6.7
I was in quarantine on suspicion of COVID-19.	Yes	171	39.5
	No	262	60.5
A relative of mine has contracted COVID-19.	Yes	351	81.1
	No	82	18.9
I lost a relative due to COVID-19.	Yes	110	25.4
	No	323	74.6
I bought, sold or rented a house during the COVID-19 period.	Yes	120	27.7
	No	313	72.3
During the COVID-19 period, I took advantage of the internet and digital technologies in buying, selling, renting and researching houses.	Yes	197	45.5
	No	236	54.5
I would like to carry out the real estate buying and selling process with computer aided systems instead of a real estate agent.	Yes	234	54
	No	199	46

Table 2 presents a set of inquiries pertaining to the covid-19 procedure that were posed to the participants, with the expectation that they would provide responses. Within the scope of this investigation, it was determined that a majority of the participants, namely 65.6% (n=284), were found to be free from the presence of the Covid-19 virus. A total of 404 individuals, accounting for 93.3% of the sample, reported having received the Covid-19 vaccination. A total

of 351 individuals, accounting for 81.1% of the sample, reported that at least one of their family members had contracted the Covid-19 virus. A total of 323 participants, accounting for 74.6% of the sample, reported that they did not experience the loss of a family member as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. The study findings revealed that a significant proportion of the participants, namely 54.5% (n=236), did not experience any advantages in using internet and digital technologies for activities like as purchasing, selling, renting, and researching properties amidst the covid-19 pandemic. A total of 313 individuals, accounting for 72.3% of the sample, reported refraining from engaging in any transactions related to purchasing, selling, or renting residential properties during the duration of the Covid-19 pandemic. A majority of the participants (54%, n=234) expressed a preference for using computer assisted solutions rather than relying on real estate agents for the facilitation of real estate purchasing and selling processes.

Research Model

The present study aimed to examine the potential mediating influence of COVID-19 fear on the relationship between decision-making styles and real estate client expectations.

Research model

Figure 1. Research Model (Respectively; Rational decision making, Intuitive decision making, Dependent decision making, Quick decision making, Afraid to make decisions, --- Fear of Covid, --- Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies)

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Research model validity analyzes

The researchers used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to assess the construct validity of the scale. Initially, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was undertaken to investigate the disentanglement of the latent constructs underlying the items within the measurement scale. The KMO value of the scale is 0.82, indicating the impact of the EFA. The Bartlett test statistic for the scale was determined to be 5719.855, with a p-value less than 0.001. The use of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) revealed that the scale had seven distinct sub-factors, as shown in Table 13. The sub-factors account for 76% of the overall variation seen in the scale. When considering the variance explained ratio, the dimensions may be arranged in descending order based on their respective explanation ratios. The dimension labeled "BEK" has the greatest explanation ratio of 19%, followed by the first dimension with an explanation ratio of 10.46%, denoted as the second dimension "CVC", and finally the third dimension with an explanation ratio of 9.88%. The fourth dimension, denoted as "CK," exhibits a disclosure rate of 9.47%. Similarly, the fifth dimension, represented by "SKV," has a disclosure rate of 9.27%. The sixth dimension, labeled as "BKV," displays a disclosure rate of 9.08%. Lastly, the dimension with the lowest disclosure rate stands at 8.88%. The size in question is often referred to as the "HKV" size.

A total of 31 items, including more than half of the scale (55 items), were excluded from the analysis due to their factor loadings falling below the threshold of 0.80. Furthermore, these items were shown to be significantly related with other factors in the scale. The scale consists of seven dimensions, each with a different number of objects. The first dimension, labeled "BEK," contains six items. The second dimension, labeled "KVK," consists of three items. The third dimension, labeled "RKV," also contains three items. The fourth dimension, labeled "CK," consists of three items. The fifth dimension, labeled "SKV," consists of three items as well. The sixth dimension, labeled "BKV," contains three items. Lastly, the seventh dimension, labeled "HKV," consists of three items. Table 11 presents the findings of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted on the scale.

Table3. EFA results of the scale for the model

Sub-Dimensions	1. Factor	2. Factor	3. Factor	4. Factor	5. Factor	6. Factor	7. Factor

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BEK9	0.880						
BEK10	0.873						
BEK7	0.865						
BEK8	0.861						
BEK12	0.849						
BEK13	0.826						
KVK2		0.884					
KVK3		0.862					
KVK5		0.850					
RKV3			0.882				
RKV4			0.836				
RKV5			0.816				
CK1				0.881			
CK2				0.855			
CK5				0.851			
SKV1					0.859		
SKV2					0.834		
SKV5					0.812		
BKV3						0.839	
BKV4						0.828	
BKV5						0.812	
HKV1							0.824
HKV2							0.821
HKV3							0.810
Total	4,566	2,511	2,373	2,273	2,225	2,179	2,131
Explained Variance (%)	19,025	10,464	9,889	9,470	9,271	9,079	8,878
Cumulative Explained Variance (%)	19,025	29,489	39,378	48,849	58,120	67,199	76,076

KMO Test Value			0.822				
Bartlett Sphericity Test Value			5719,855				
Bartlett test p Value			0.001				

Table 4. Model Factor Distribution

Factor 1: BEK	
BEK 7:	I would like the real estate company website or mobile application to provide information about the energy efficiency of buildings listed for sale and rent.
BEK 8:	I would like to have a system on the real estate company website or mobile application that compares the price increase trends in the region I am interested in for the last ten years and shows the forecasts for the future.
BEK 9:	I would like to have a system installed on the real estate company website or mobile application, which calculates the income I will gain by comparing the existing investment tools with real estate investment.
BEK 10:	On the real estate company website or mobile application, I would like to show the customer references and the opinions of the customers who have shopped about the construction company and the real estate company before.
BEK 12:	I would like real estate and construction companies to have QR codes on their signs, advertisements and business cards, so that I can access they're for sale and rental lists.
BEK 13:	I would like their help and advice on decision making through recommendation systems on the real estate company website or mobile application.
Factor 2: KVK	
KVK 2:	I postpone making decisions as long as possible.
KVK 3:	I often postpone important decisions.
KVK 5:	I put off many decisions because thinking about them makes me uncomfortable.
Factor 3: RKV	
RKV 3:	I make decisions logically and systematically.
RKV 4:	I need to think carefully before making a decision.
RKV 5:	I consider various options when making a decision on an issue.
Factor 4: CK	

CK 1:	I am afraid of contracting COVID-19.
CK2:	Thinking about COVID-19 bothers me.
CK 5:	I get nervous and anxious when I watch news and stories about COVID-19 on social media.
Factor 5: SKV	
SC 1:	I trust my instincts when making decisions.
SC 2:	I usually tend to trust my intuition when making decisions.
SKV 5:	I trust my gut reactions when making a decision.
Factor 6: BKV	
BKV 3:	It is easier for me to make important decisions when I have the support of others.
BKV 4:	I use the advice of others when making important decisions.
BKV 5:	I like having someone to point me in the right direction when I'm faced with important decisions.
Factor 7: HKV	
HKV 1:	I usually make sudden decisions.
HKV 2:	I often make split-second decisions.
HKV 3:	I make quick decisions.

Table 11 displays the results of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted using the data gathered from the research participants. The findings of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) reveal that the scale has seven distinct sub-factors. The "IEC" sub-factor of the scale has six items, with factor load values ranging from 0.826 to 0.880. This sub-factor accounts for 19% of the overall variation. The second element is referred to as "KVK," which has a total of three items. The factor loading values exhibit a range of 0.850 to 0.884, and together account for 10.46% of the overall variation. The third component is referred to as "RCV," which encompasses a sub-factor including three distinct elements. The factor loading values exhibit a range of 0.816 to 0.882, collectively accounting for 9.88% of the explained total variation. The fourth component in this study is referred to as "CK" and it has a total of three elements. The factor loading values of the items associated with this factor exhibit a range of 0.851 to 0.881, accounting for 9.47% of the overall discriminative variance. The fifth component is referred to

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as "SKV" and it encompasses a sub-factor that comprises three distinct things. The factor loading values of the items associated with this factor range from 0.812 to 0.859, and together account for 9.27% of the total variance. The sixth element, denoted as "BKV," comprises a set of three distinct items. The factor load values of the items pertaining to this dimension exhibit a range from 0.812 to 0.839, and they together account for 9.08% of the total variance. The seventh component, denoted as "HKV," encompasses a sub-factor that comprises three distinct entries. The factor loading values of the items associated with this factor range from 0.810 to 0.824, and together account for 8.88% of the total variance. Consequently, a total of seven variables accounts for 76% of the overall variation.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used to examine the structure of the scale, resulting in the identification and determination of sub-factors. A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted in order to assess the precision of the components identified via exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and to see whether they constituted a valid measurement model. The DFA analysis was conducted using the AMOS 24 software suite. Prior to conducting parameter estimates in confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), a preliminary assessment was conducted to ascertain the suitability of the data for a multivariate normal distribution. This assessment was crucial in determining the most acceptable approach for parameter estimation. The findings pertaining to the multivariate normal distribution are shown in Table 13. The multivariate normal distribution fit test yielded a p-value of 0.0001 and a z-value of 54,535. Based on the acquired values, it was deduced that the data did not exhibit multivariate normal distribution. In this particular instance, the Maximum Likelihood approach was used for analysis.

Table 5. CRÖ multivariate normality values

	kurtosis	Z value
AMOS	185,171	54,535

The researchers used the Primary level CFA (Confirmatory Factor Analysis) technique to assess the validity and reliability of the measurement scale utilized in examining the potential mediating role of fear of Covid in the relationship between decision-making styles and real estate clients' expectations about digital technologies. The analysis outcomes and route map for

the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) at the primary level are shown in Figure 5 and Table 14, respectively.

Figure 2. Primary level CFA and Standardized Values for the Model

CK: Fear of Covid; RKV: Rational Decision Making; SKV: Intuitive Decision Making; BKV: Dependent Decision Making; KVK: Avoidance of Decision Making; HKV: Quick Decision Making; BEK: Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies

Initially, an examination was conducted on the fit index values for model II. Among the many index values, two often used measures of model fit are the Normed Fit Index (NFI) and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) are both commonly used measures in the field of statistics and psychometrics to

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assess the fit of a statistical model to a given dataset. The Goodness of Fit Index, sometimes referred to as AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index), is a statistical measure used to assess the degree to which an observed data set matches an expected theoretical model. The GFI value was adjusted by considering the sample size. The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is a statistical measure used in academic research to assess the fit of a structural equation model. The square root of the standardized mean errors, often known as RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error Approximation), The root means square error of approximation, denoted as χ^2 / sd , is calculated by dividing the chi-square value by the degrees of freedom.

Table 6. Primary level CFA fit indices and results

Index	Good Fit	Acceptable Fit	Results
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI \leq 0.95$	0.93
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0.97
GFI	$0.90 \leq GFI \leq 0.95$	$0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	0.93
AGFI	$0.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$0.85 \leq AGFI \leq 0.90$	0.91
SRMR	$0.00 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.04
RMSEA	$0.00 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.04
χ^2 / sd	$0 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 3$	1.73

Prior to conducting the structural equation modeling (SEM) test, a measurement model was developed and examined to assess the co-modelability of the elements inside the structural model. Upon examination of the values obtained in the analysis, it is observed that the calculated value for the measurement model's χ^2 is 398,533, while the degrees of freedom are 231 (resulting in a χ^2/df ratio of 1.725). The expression " χ^2 " refers to the square of the variable " Given that the value is influenced by the sample size, the criteria chosen for analysis was the χ^2 / sd value, which is less susceptible to the impact of sample size. Upon examination of additional goodness of fit indices for the measurement model (RMSEA = 0.040; SRMR = 0.04; NFI = 0.93; CFI = 0.97; GFI = 0.93; AGFI = 0.91), it was concluded that the model demonstrated an adequate degree of fit. Consequently, due to the compatibility of the measurement model, the structural model was used.

Analysis Results Regarding the Structural Model

Hypotheses tested in the research model

H1: Fear of Covid has a mediating effect between rational decision making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H2: Fear of Covid has a mediating effect between intuitive decision making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H3: Fear of Covid has a mediating effect between quick decision making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H4: Fear of Covid has a mediating effect between dependent decision making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H5: Fear of Covid has a mediating effect between decision-making avoidance and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

The claimed hypotheses were examined according to the values resulting from the structural model. The structural model including standardized values is given in Figure 3.

Chi-Square: 410,417 df: 234 p:0,0001 RMSEA:0,042

Figure 3. Structural model path diagram

Upon scrutinizing Figure 3, which presents the route diagram illustrating the structural model, it is seen that the coefficient ck2, with a magnitude of 0.84 on the construct CK, is associated with the statement "The contemplation of COVID-19 induces a sense of discomfort within me." The component that demonstrates the highest level of effectiveness is rkv4, as shown by its RKV rating of 0.89. The item "I need to engage in thoughtful deliberation in order to arrive at a decision" has the highest level of effectiveness, while the item "I typically rely on my intuition when making decisions" exhibits a strong correlation with a value of 0.86 on the Scale of Knowledge and Values (SKV). According to the BKV scale, bkv5 is assigned a value

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of 0.77, indicating a strong inclination towards seeking guidance from others when confronted with significant choices. This item reflects the individual's preference for having a guiding influence to steer them in the appropriate path. Similarly, bk4 is associated with the use of advice from others as a factor in the process of making crucial decisions. The elements that demonstrate the highest level of effectiveness are kvk3, as shown by their KVK rating of 0.87. The aforementioned item is often subject to delay while significant judgments are being made. Based on a value of 0.86, it was determined that the Bek10 item "I would like to access customer opinions regarding the construction company and real estate company, as well as their customer references, through the real estate company's website or mobile application" exhibited the highest level of effectiveness.

Once the essential criteria for goodness of fit indices were satisfied in the measurement model of the research, the subsequent step was conducting the structural model test. The fit index values of the structural model are shown in Table 15. One of the index values that is often used in academic research is the Normed Fit Index (NFI). The normalized fit index, CFI (Comparative Fit Index), and the goodness of fit index, GFI (Goodness of Fit Index), are both measures used in academic research to assess the fit of a statistical model to the observed data. The Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) is a statistical measure used to assess the goodness of fit of a statistical model. The GFI value was adjusted by taking into account the sample size and the SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual). The root mean square of standardized errors, also referred to as RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error Approximation), is a statistical measure used to assess the goodness of fit of a model. The root mean square of estimated errors, denoted as χ^2 / sd , is calculated by dividing the chi square by the degrees of freedom.

Table 7. Fit index values of the structural model

Index	Good Fit	Acceptable Fit	Results
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI \leq 0.95$	0.93
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0.97
GFI	$0.90 \leq GFI \leq 0.95$	$0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	0.93
AGFI	$0.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$0.85 \leq AGFI \leq 0.90$	0.91
SRMR	$0.00 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.05

RMSEA	$0.00 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.04
χ^2 / sd	$0 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 3$	1.75

The structural model's predicted value for the chi-square statistic (χ^2) is 410.417, with 234 degrees of freedom ($\chi^2/df = 1.75$). The criteria used for this analysis was the value of χ^2 / sd , since it is less influenced by the sample size. Upon examination of various goodness-of-fit indices (RMSEA= 0.040; SRMR= 0.050; NFI=0.93; CFI= 0.97; GFI=0.93; AGFI= 0.91) pertaining to the measurement model, it is evident that the model demonstrates a satisfactory degree of fit.

According to the results given in Appendix 4 at a significance level of 0.05;

H 1: Rational decision-making style affects real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies, and the fear of covid mediates this. (P<0.05)

H2: Intuitive decision-making style affects real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies, and the fear of covid mediate this. (P<0.05)

H3: Quick decision-making style does not affect real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies. (P>0.05)

H4: Dependent decision-making style affects real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies, and the fear of Covid mediates this. (P<0.05)

H5: Decision avoidance style affects the expectations of real estate customers from digital technologies and fear of covid mediates this. (P<0.05)

Upon examining the results obtained from the analysis of five hypotheses (H1, H2, H4, and H5), it was found that these hypotheses, which propose that the fear of COVID-19 acts as a mediator between rational decision making, intuitive decision making, avoidance of decision making, and dependent decision making, as well as real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies, were accepted at a significance level of 0.05.

Research model reliability analyzes

In order for a scale to be considered appropriate for use, it is essential that it have both validity and reliability. The validity analyses led to the conclusion that the Model II scale is a viable instrument. Hence, to ascertain the scale's reliability, the Cronbach Alpha (CA) test is used. The CA test serves the purpose of assessing the reliability of the scale. The study analyzed the internal consistency coefficient, obtained from the binary correlation, as well as the Combined Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. The Cronbach Alpha (CA) values of the scale are shown in Table 17.

Table 8. Evaluation of scale reliability according to alpha value (Özdamar, 2017)

$\alpha < 0.50$	The scale is unreliable
$0.50 \leq \alpha < 0.60$	The scale is low reliable.
$0.60 \leq \alpha < 0.70$	The scale is moderately reliable
$0.70 \leq \alpha < 0.80$	The scale is reliable at a generally accepted level.
$0.80 \leq \alpha < 0.90$	The scale is highly reliable.
$\alpha \geq 0.90$	The scale is perfectly reliable.

Table 9. CA values of the model scale

Factor	Number of items	CA (Cronbach Alpha)
BACK	6	0.93
KVK	3	0.87
RKV	3	0.85
CK	3	0.84
SKV	3	0.83
BKV	3	0.81
HKV	3	0.81
full scale	24	0.80

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Upon examination of Table 17, one can see the presence of reliability values assigned to both individual factors as well as the overall scale. Based on the observed reliability values above the threshold of 0.70, it may be inferred that the scale under consideration has a satisfactory level of dependability. In situations when there is a substantial quantity of items, the usage of coefficient omega hierarchical (CR) may serve as a viable substitute for coefficient alpha (CA), also known as Cronbach's alpha. The construct reliability value, also referred to as composite reliability, is another term used to describe this measure. The CR (Combined Reliability) value must exceed 0.70, similar to the CA (Cronbach Alpha) number. The AVE (average explained variance) is calculated by dividing the factor-related expressions by the total of the squared covariances. According to Hair (1998), it is anticipated that the Average Explained Variance (AVE) values would surpass 0.50. Table 18 presents the values of CR (Combined Reliability) and AVE (Average Explained Variance) for the factors.

Table 3. CR and AVE values for the factors of the Model Scale

Sub-Factors	CR (Combined Reliability)	AVE (Average Explained Variance)
BACK	0.94	0.74
KVK	0.90	0.75
RKV	0.88	0.71
CK	0.90	0.74
SKV	0.87	0.70
BKV	0.87	0.68
HKV	0.86	0.67

Upon examination of Table 18, it becomes evident that the scale exhibits a satisfactory level of general reliability, as shown by the fact that the Combined Reliability (CR) values exceed 0.70 and the Mean Explained Variance (AVE) values surpass 0.50.

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RESTRICTION

In this study, which is built around a better understanding of the relationship between the phenomena of power and social control, the boundaries of these two concepts are determined and this evaluation is carried out with the information provided from the sources obtained by taking into account the scope of the research. This study is globally limited to the scientific studies on the subject.

NOTICES

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external experts.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Financial Support: The author did not report any financial support for the study.

ETHICS DECLARATION

The publication ethics of this journal; It is a scientific journal in the field of social sciences that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with the main criteria specified as openness, honesty, respect for the findings and work of other publishers and objectivity.

CONCLUSION

This research aimed to examine the mediating role of fear of COVID-19 in the relationship between decision-making styles and real estate clients' expectations of digital technology. The study findings indicate that the fear of COVID-19 has a mediating role in the relationship between decision avoidance types (rational, intuitive, and dependent) and real

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estate clients' expectations about digital technology. However, it should be noted that this mediating impact is not seen in the case of the rapid decision-making style.

It might be argued that individuals who want to evade decision-making in fear-inducing contexts anticipate receiving information from digital technology that reinforces their inclination towards such avoidance. The dependent decision-making style is characterized by an increased reliance on external help in unpredictable environments, such as the one caused by the Covid-19 outbreak. This heightened demand for assistance extends beyond self-reliance and places more expectations on digital technology.

Individuals who possess an intuitive decision-making style have heightened expectations towards digital technology when confronted with factors such as the apprehension around the Covid-19 pandemic. The decision-making style characterized by intuition is intrinsically linked to emotions, and the apprehension surrounding the Covid-19 pandemic might potentially induce adverse emotional outcomes. Efforts aimed at mitigating the aforementioned adverse circumstances and minimizing uncertainty may result in heightened expectations about the capabilities of digital technology.

The acceptance of the hypothesis posits that there is a relationship between rational decision-making style and consumers' expectations about digital technology. The utilization of the rational decision-making style, characterized by the logical assessment of accurate and desired information within a Covid-mediated environment, may result in heightened expectations among real estate customers regarding the efficacy of digital technologies. This is driven by the desire to mitigate the presence of insecure information and unpredictability.

The presence of fear may be posited as a hindrance to the adoption of a rapid decision-making approach, perhaps leading to the deferral of decision-making due to heightened levels of uncertainty.

Contributions of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its execution at a pivotal juncture within the realm of real estate marketing. Furthermore, given the limited number of studies conducted on real

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estate marketing within the Turkish literature, it is anticipated that this research will make substantial contributions to the subject.

The study is anticipated to provide valuable insights for those engaged in academic research within the realm of real estate marketing, digital media designers specializing in real estate marketing, real estate brokers, and scholars investigating the social and economic ramifications of epidemics.

Suggestions

Digital media designers in real estate marketing must consider various decision-making methods for distinct circumstances, while also taking into consideration a wide range of settings and conditions. From a marketing perspective, real estate marketers have the challenge of addressing and mitigating the preference of clients to adopt decision-avoidance methods, hence forgoing other decision-making approaches. The primary responsibility of a marketer is to use persuasive techniques in order to influence customers' decision-making processes and provide assistance along the decision-making journey. It is important to elucidate the advantages that customers would get by opting to make a purchase rather of deferring their choice. When elucidating the advantages to be gained, it is important to provide comprehensive information that caters to the rational decision-making style. Conversely, in the realm of digital environment designs, it is crucial to incorporate elements that appeal to the emotions of customers with intricate emotional states, as per the requirements of the intuitive decision-making style. The incorporation of expert viewpoints is recommended for individuals who use a dependent decision-making style, as it may complement the rational decision-making approach. Furthermore, clients should possess the capability to substantiate their conclusions by using expert systems that align with the information they have gathered. Customers adopt the dependent decision-making style when they seek assistance from others in order to validate their choices or when they have uncertainty over the accuracy of their decision-making process.

When formulating digital environments for real estate marketing, it may be deemed inappropriate to categorize clients based on their decision-making style as either logical or intuitive. It is important to consider all decision-making styles when designing digital media and content. Additionally, it is crucial to do research on mixed decision-making systems. To

optimize the impact of digital media material, it is advantageous to tailor it to each decision-making style, taking into consideration the influence of various elements.

Resource

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